

Deliverable

D4.2 Findings of the stakeholder dialogues

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Executive Summary

Effective stakeholder engagement is essential if PRO-Ethics is to have a lasting sustainable impact. PRO-Ethics needs to draw on the expertise of organisations outside the consortium to develop a robust ethics framework and practical usable guidelines for assessing the ethics of participation in innovation processes. Its wider impact also depends on results being used by organisations beyond the consortium. Work Package 4 is designed to ensure that key stakeholders are meaningfully involved in PRO-Ethics from an early stage and throughout the project.

Task 4.2 aimed to engage key external stakeholders, specifically research funding and research practising organisations, policymakers, civil society organisations and other non-governmental organisations (NGOs), for the purpose of gathering feedback on PRO-Ethics activities and outputs in development and to widen the consortium network. To achieve this aim, three workshops were delivered during the life-cycle of the PRO-Ethics project.

While the design of the workshop activities centred on the needs of the external stakeholders invited to participate, all findings and insights served to support the learning and iteration of activities led by the wider PRO-Ethics consortium. This report summarises the key lessons learned from external stakeholders engaged, explains how insights were embedded in the development of PRO-Ethics' framework and guidelines and reflects on wider lessons from the delivery of this Task.

1 Introduction

PRO-Ethics is working with research and innovation funding organisations across Europe to test new, ethical ways to involve citizens in three fields of action: participation in innovation projects, participation in strategy development and participation in evaluation processes. PRO-Ethics will deliver an ethics framework, together with a set of practical guidelines and actionable criteria for assessing the quality and ethics of participation processes.

PRO-Ethics' project design includes pilots, which serve as the mechanism to test and evaluate the ways research funding organisations (part of the PRO-Ethics consortium) engage citizens in three fields of action, which are categorised in PRO-Ethics as strategy development, evaluation processes, and R&I projects. Lessons from the pilots shape the ethical framework that aims to provide information on how to deal with a diversity of views on ethics and participatory processes, and the diversity of practices of research funding organisations. The pilots also form the basis for the guidelines that accompany the ethics framework, which includes actionable reflections on how to consider ethical aspects before, during and after stakeholder participation. In light of this approach, it was also essential to ensure that the guidelines served other key external stakeholders outside of the consortium, such as civil society, other research funding organisations and policymakers.

The objective of PRO-Ethics Task 4.2 has been to engage potential external stakeholders throughout the whole project. Here, we looked to ensure the needs and priorities of civil society, other research performing and funding organisations and policymakers fed into and informed the development of the ethical framework at different stages of the project. This task was intended to increase the legitimacy of the framework and enable PRO-Ethics to draw on a wider range of views and ideas as it was being developed.

Task 4.2 comprised three dialogue and engagement workshops, scheduled to be held in months 13, 16 and 39 of the project. The planned focus of the first workshop was to share a preliminary version of the draft ethics framework and documented experiences of the first pilot phase, while the second workshop aimed to critically review ethical aspects of the pilot plans. The third and final workshop aimed to engage external stakeholders with a near complete version of the ethics framework, to discuss lessons learned from applying the framework to the research funding organisation (RFO) pilots.

Task 4.2 ran from month five of the PRO-Ethics project (May 2020) to month 40 (April 2023). Over this time, PRO-Ethics partners delivering this task (Nesta, EUREKA, EUREC Office and ZSI) designed and ran three interactive workshops to engage different key stakeholder groups for the project. All three workshops took place online.

This report summarises findings from the three workshops, and how they were applied to the development of other PRO-Ethics deliverables. It also reports on the impact of engagement activities in this Task, and how they have contributed to broadening awareness of the project to key stakeholders beyond the consortium network.

2 Activities

The activities were designed to be mutually beneficial to ensure participants, regardless of background, gained value from interacting with PRO-Ethics and were encouraged to engage with the project and its outputs in the future. The aim was to build a meaningful network that would increase the likelihood of PRO-Ethics' driving impact beyond the four-year project life cycle. While gathering input and feedback on the ethical framework and guidelines in development was of high importance, participants' needs were used as the starting point to choose the length, content and style of workshop delivery. Peer learning and information sharing played a central role in allowing the workshops to remain dynamic in purpose and shaped by the needs of participants in attendance.

2.1 Workshop 1: Citizen participation in innovation

Workshop 1 '*Citizen participation in innovation*' took place online. It featured presentations from PRO-Ethics partners who were designing and running pilots involving citizens in R&I activities, which were supplemented with structured discussion around a draft version of the PRO-Ethics framework. The aim of the workshop was to gather insight on the potential applicability of the framework and suggestions for how it could be improved. PRO-Ethics partners were joined by organisations from across Europe, including the OECD, and research funding organisations (RFOs) in Belgium, Germany, Latvia, Norway, Serbia, Spain and the United Kingdom. Some stakeholders had experience of involving citizens in their activities, while others were only starting to consider ways they might do the same. We captured individual RFO experiences of involving citizens in their activities¹ in a worksheet that was used to gather insights that were shared in the wider group discussion.

2.2 Workshop 2: Success markers to involve citizens in R&I

As the second round of pilots² were being designed by PRO-Ethics' partners, organisations with experience of involving citizens in their work were brought together in an online workshop to feed in their knowledge and explore key questions PRO-Ethics partners were likely to face. Workshop 2 '*Success markers to involve citizens in R&I*' explored three key themes:

1. The purpose of participation
2. How to build trust with communities
3. How to structure processes for successful participation

The stakeholders involved included research, funding and citizen science organisations from 11 different countries. All who joined workshop 2 had some experience of involving citizens in a variety of contexts from local government to living labs and science centres.

2.3 Workshop 3: Guidelines for citizen participation

Workshop 3 '*Guidelines for citizen participation*' brought together research and innovation experts. With this final workshop, PRO-Ethics was interested in both the individual experience of participating organisations involving citizens in R&I, and their first thoughts on the ethics framework and guidelines

¹ In the context of PRO-Ethics, RFOs' activities (processes) refer to programme/funding scheme development and implementation (launch of the call, reception of proposals, proposal selection), as well as strategic planning (including grants/programme management).

² See <https://pro-ethics.eu/pilots/pilots-phase-2> and PRO-Ethics deliverable D2.4 Reports on Pilot II Results.

that were available in the second draft form. While the first version of the ethics framework had been shared in workshop 1, the document had been further developed, aligned and streamlined in the meanwhile. The presentation focused on the guidelines which had been fine-tuned as a result of the needs highlighted by research funding organisations. The experts who joined us in workshop 3 included organisations who had experience of involving citizens in specific projects. The draft guidelines were shared ahead of time to ensure that the discussion and feedback was specific to the version of the ethical framework and guidelines in development.

Detailed workshop agendas and materials delivered may be found in Annex 2 and Annex 3.

3 Insights

Of the three stakeholder dialogue workshops implemented in the course of PRO-Ethics, two were held early in year two (months 13 and 16 of the project) and one at the beginning of year four (month 36). Insights gathered from the first two workshops were summarised and reported back in the form of recommendations to Work Packages 1 and 5, which are tasked with the development of the ethics framework and guidelines. PRO-Ethics consortium partners also joined the stakeholder workshops to share their experiences and hear first-hand how other peer organisations, outside of the consortium, were considering citizen participation and the success markers of citizen participation (feeding into their own pilots in Work Package 2). The final workshop was co-designed with the team at TUD (leading Work Package 5) and ensured full participation of the team drafting the final framework. Insights from all engagements are summarised below.

3.1 Before participation

Even before citizen participation is considered by civil society, research funding organisations and policymakers, getting started requires groundwork to set the stage for citizen participation to even be a viable option for integration in existing research and innovation activities and processes. The insights below reflect the challenges and needs of RFOs conducting R&I activities and citizens that may be approached to participate.

Making the case for why citizens should be involved in R&I

Making the case for citizen participation is required before existing processes that have seldom involved citizens in the past can be transformed within research funding organisations. In workshop 1, stakeholders told PRO-Ethics that while citizen engagement is becoming more and more important, it is often difficult to gather sufficient buy-in from those designing and delivering activities and those overseeing strategic decisions. Therefore, proving the exact value that citizens and stakeholders bring to a project was suggested to be one of the biggest barriers faced by those who wish to champion great citizen participation. There is general agreement that participation can be helpful to build legitimacy for innovation outputs but this argument alone was often not enough to convince sceptics, particularly if leadership is not on board.

Understanding when to involve citizens

Similar to the need to pinpoint the exact value of citizen participation, RFOs told PRO-Ethics that the framework should be clear about when citizen participation is needed. What kinds of projects should citizens be involved in, at what stages and to what degree, were all live questions for the RFOs in the workshops run by PRO-Ethics. Having clarity on when an area of innovation *must* involve citizen participation (as opposed to when it would be nice to have, or indeed when it wouldn't be appropriate) would be beneficial to the RFOs and to citizens to ensure that their value is maximised and communicated accordingly.

During the workshop discussions on what practical conditions needed to be in place for successful citizen participation (diving deeper into the questions of when to involve citizens), there were mixed feelings about whether citizens should be involved in co-defining challenges in the very earliest stages or whether to wait until a research or funding organisation had a set project objective. This is because there are valid reasons for doing both.

Figure 1: Example responses from a workshop activity exploring when research funders should involve citizens in their work

3.2 During participation

Shedding light on how limited resources can be maximised

During the stakeholder engagement workshops, external RFOs commented that they often lack the time to properly consider participation, its purpose and the value for it. Those still thinking about whether to involve citizens at all found the perceived lack of time and resources to be one of the biggest barriers to getting started. As one participant commented, participation is 'often a nice-to-have that doesn't get off the ground'. The framework would therefore be useful if it provided simple step-by-step guidance for time-poor RFOs, and concrete examples of the guidelines' application.

Creating consensus about what participation means

Both within individual organisations and between RFOs, having a shared language to discuss participation was identified as something that was needed for several reasons. First, it would help facilitate conversations with those who needed to be convinced in order to gain sufficient buy-in. Second, sharing the same language would help RFOs to learn from each other. Third, a shared understanding of terminology as well as processes would also enable conversations with other important institutional stakeholders in the process, such as research ethics and research integrity organisations. Finally, clarity about citizen participation and any associated terms would also help to communicate better with citizens being approached to participate in R&I activities.

Highlighting where citizen engagement is useful with real-life examples

In almost all workshops, civil society representatives, RFOs and policymakers alike mentioned the need for real-life case studies of citizen participation that they could learn from and replicate. Having examples of how others included participation in their projects would provide weight to an ethical

framework's guidance beyond the abstract. Particular concerns, such as participative processes being hijacked by lobbyists or citizens not being involved in a meaningful way, were raised as risks RFOs were unsure how to mitigate against. The lessons from the pilots that informed PRO-Ethics would have to be illustrated in concrete ways, to ensure lessons derived and informing the ethics framework and guideline could be understood by those who had not been involved in the consortium's activities.

Ensuring value for citizens involved in R&I activities (and suggested pathways to achieve this)

There are many ways to consider "value", but when it comes to citizen participation, it is important that research and funding organisations consider value from the perspective of all those involved – not just the value obtained for a particular R&I project or funding agency process. While the input of lived experience can enrich research and its subsequent end products, what will those who participate get in return? This was an important question that was raised by discussions with external stakeholders and is a consideration that would be relevant to any project.

Experts who have previous experience involving citizens in R&I activities also provided insights on how to address these central questions. First, experts told PRO-Ethics that citizen participation can be approached in many different ways and while there are different levels of engagements, from full co-creation to consultations, when a project directly affects a community (or will have a resulting effect on them) citizen participation is crucial. Here the value is clear to all who need to be communicated with. Second, to ensure participation is meaningful, experts advised that citizens should be involved when there is a prototype of a solution, service or policy that people can practically be involved with. This ensures citizens see the tangible value of their input within a larger process or body of work.

Practical step-by-step guidance for successful citizen participation

There was widespread agreement that projects involving citizens needed to have a clear plan for how citizens would participate. Having a process to manage citizen input would always be key. How would citizen feedback be tracked and used in research and innovation, and how would research and funding organisations communicate this process with those involved? These are central questions that any project would need to answer.

Another practical consideration relates to making the process for participation accessible, in order to ensure that citizens are motivated to get involved. Remuneration is also a way to make sure that those who are involved represent a balanced group of society; without remuneration, only involving those who can afford to participate for free will do so.

Figure 2: Example responses from a workshop activity exploring practical requirements when involving citizens in R&I activities

3.3 After participation

Centring learning and iteration

Ultimately, there are many practical considerations to take into account that informed the actionable reflections in the guidelines produced by PRO-Ethics. There were also lots of insights on ways participation can go wrong. Therefore, regular reflection and review was suggested as the best way to build and iterate on the structure of participative projects. Leaving room for adaptation that fits citizen needs is also important.

Continued engagement and trust building beyond on-off R&I activities

Experts that had extensive experience of involving citizens (for example the various civil society organisations who joined the stakeholder engagement sessions) raised the importance of considering engaged citizens beyond a project life cycle. How would citizens be informed of how their input fed into R&I activities? How would the communities formed for the purpose of R&I activities be further supported or closed down “well”? These were live questions that external stakeholders posed to PRO-Ethics to consider. Experts told PRO-Ethics that trust would be one of the most important elements for successful participation with any community and that this should be the priority for research and innovation projects that involve those with lived experience. Being transparent about how citizen input will be used and communicating with the same communities after a research project has been completed are all practical ways to help build solid relationships between communities and the innovation sector.

4 Embedding insights in the ethics framework and guidelines

Insights from the stakeholder engagement workshops have been applied in three distinct ways. First, insights helped shape the ethics framework and guidelines by validating areas where actionable reflections were needed to ensure usability and helped to indicate where the guidelines would need to be made more accessible. Second, the workshops helped to map where the guidelines could connect to other resources and tools being used to ensure ethical practices in research and innovation activities. Finally, engaging with other experts outside the PRO-Ethics consortium helped PRO-Ethics partners sense-check their own pilot designs and delivery plans. Insights from the engagement workshops were also used for communication purposes to ensure PRO-Ethics was sharing lessons with the wider research and innovation ecosystem throughout the project life cycle.

4.1 Shaping the ethics framework and guidelines

The insights gathered from the stakeholder engagement workshops validates the need raised by PRO-Ethics pilots for actionable reflections to accompany the ethics framework and guidelines. The purpose of this addition has been to ensure usability of both the framework (theory) and guidelines (practical application). The insights gathered also made clear that the final outputs would need to be made more accessible.

1. **Ideal application vs practical reality:** We heard that the guidelines may offer ideal cases that many research funding and practicing organisations might struggle to implement in their entirety. Research funding organisations for example may consider adding ethical requirements to proposals but they might still play less of an active role in ensuring ethical application in funded works. Therefore, the guidelines would benefit from thinking about all the different actors' use cases from funders, down to specific researchers. Templates and other useful practical resources could support this.
2. **Consideration of the platform:** The platform where the final guidelines will live will play a big role in the final use of this resource. Considering an accessible format online, potentially as a toolkit or an interface, as well as the original document form, would support both use and sharing of the guidelines. A platform could ensure that the guidelines speak the same language to the different target groups in a way that is easy to understand and navigate, allowing each target group to get what they need.
3. **Examples vs. questions:** Mirroring feedback also gathered from the research ethics and integrity experts, we heard again that the open questions in the guidelines might only be useful to advanced users. Concrete examples with "more flesh" would be needed to help those who have no idea about where to start gathering ideas on how to apply citizen engagement principles to their work.

4.2 Referencing other tools

In the second stakeholder engagement workshop, participants were invited to share existing resources they used to ensure the ethical participation of citizens in R&I activities. The shared resources fell into three main categories:

1. **Internal organisational guidance:** For example, universities with ethics boards had their own ethics guidelines and processes (e.g., committees) that helped to ensure ethical research

practices. This guidance tended to focus on research practices more than research funding practices.

2. **Local and national guidance** as developed by steering committees and policymakers.
3. **International guides and tools** such as the ALLEA Code of Conduct that are adapted to concrete national and organisational contexts.

4.3 Supporting iterative learning and knowledge exchange within the PRO-Ethics consortium

The input of experts engaged in citizen participation outside the PRO-Ethics consortium helped PRO-Ethics partners to sense-check their own pilot designs and delivery plans. The exchange of challenges being faced by PRO-Ethics' research funding organisations with external stakeholders facing similar questions was mutually beneficial; external stakeholders got real-life examples to gather insights from and PRO-Ethics partners gathered ideas on how to overcome barriers they were facing, often for the first time. As the topics PRO-Ethics covers are an emerging focus area for R&I, knowing what challenges are common or if such activities might face similar barriers in organisations outside the consortium was essential for the iteration of the final ethics framework and guidelines.

Insights from the engagement workshops were also used for communication purposes such as blogposts on the project website to ensure PRO-Ethics was sharing lessons and emerging insights with the wider research and innovation ecosystem throughout the project life cycle.

5 Reflections from delivering Task 4.2

What went well

The key objective for work package 4 was to support the translation of project results into practical outputs that were robust and widely applicable across the EU and internationally. Task 4.2 specifically focused on ensuring potential external stakeholders (other RFOs, policymakers, civil society organisations and NGOs) were engaged throughout the entire PRO-Ethics project. PRO-Ethics wanted to increase legitimacy for the ethics framework and guidelines and draw in a wide range of views and ideas.

Despite the design for Task 4.2 having envisioned the delivery of stakeholder engagement events face-to-face (prior to the Covid-19 pandemic), we achieved great success with all activities being delivered online. Moving engagement online enabled PRO-Ethics to reach stakeholders from many different countries and contexts from the start. The online mode of delivery was a more convenient way to bring together a wide variety of stakeholders for dialogue in one space.

The online workshop format also meant that we could better capture smaller breakout group discussions, using tools such as Miro, Zoom polls and screen capture, to effectively record insights and quickly share results back with the rest of the PRO-Ethics consortium. This facilitated the embedding of the full range of findings in the development of the PRO-Ethics framework and guidelines and pilot designs.

What could have been improved and lessons learned

While there were benefits from engaging stakeholders online, there were also drawbacks. Namely, it was difficult to replicate the organic networking that is often the biggest incentive for stakeholders engaging in projects outside of the ones they are directly impacted by. This meant that PRO-Ethics had to continuously consider creative ways to ensure stakeholders gained value for participation in the workshops being run.

The first draft of the ethics framework and guidelines used for workshop 1 wasn't quite at a stage for external dissemination. Therefore, the framework was presented in the workshop but not shared in advance. This decision made it hard to gather concrete feedback on the content of the framework, rather than more abstract ideas of its potential application. During the first two workshops, PRO-Ethics pilots were also not at a stage where concrete insights could be shared. Therefore, the first two workshops were harder to prepare for as PRO-Ethics had fewer materials or plans to gather feedback on.

A key lesson learned was how to focus engaged stakeholders on the wider debates surrounding the involvement of citizens and non-traditional stakeholders in R&I activities – why, for what purpose and when to engage citizens – to gather useful insights that would still shape the development of the concrete outputs from PRO-Ethics. We also learned to connect and target invites to stakeholders working on other EU projects related to citizen engagement, to ensure we captured and shared lessons with experts already working on similar challenges.

6 Conclusions

From the stakeholder engagement workshops with civil society, research funding organisations and policymakers it was clear that the PRO-Ethics framework and guidelines have the potential to be both useful and used as a reference tool. In order to achieve this, PRO-Ethics learned that it would be helpful if the framework and guidelines could provide a clear rationale for why citizens and stakeholders should be involved in research and innovation processes and practices; how they can be brought in in a meaningful way with step-by-step guidance and case studies to support application; and reflective tools for iterative learning.

While there was a fair amount of overlap between the experiences of other RFOs and what PRO-Ethics' research had uncovered, the dialogue workshops provided further depth to pilot findings, as well as shedding light on alternative perspectives. For example, when considering successful citizen participation, keep in mind the purpose of participation, thinking about how to build trust with communities and how to structure the participation process itself. In all these areas, external experts helped inform the development of the PRO-Ethics framework and guidelines. There are many challenges that citizen participation is likely to surface so there needs to be careful consideration from the start of any such process. As research and innovation begins to involve citizens in more of its activities, organisations must be aware of potential participation fatigue – when the same communities are asked to contribute for little return time after time. External stakeholders helped keep PRO-Ethics focused on the wider picture, beyond the activities of research funding organisations alone.

The stakeholder engagement workshops uncovered insights that:

- ▶ Shaped the PRO-Ethics ethics framework and guidelines
- ▶ Widened the resources used to support both theoretical and practical aspects of the framework and guidelines
- ▶ Supported the iteration of PRO-Ethics activities throughout the four-year project life cycle

In parallel to supporting the development of PRO-Ethics, the engagement workshops also widened our network and supported engagement beyond the consortium. In particular, the workshops connected PRO-Ethics to other EU projects where there were synergies between our work, ensuring we build on existing expertise and share our perspectives with those confronting similar topic areas.

Annex 1: List of participating organisations

Organisation	Location
Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Austrian Agency for International Cooperation in Education (OeAD)	Austria
VLAIO	Belgium
Tomas Bata University	Czech Republic
Estonian Academy of Sciences	Estonia
Tampere University	Finland
Learning Planet Institute	France
Project Juelich	Germany
Science Foundation Ireland	Ireland
Politecnico di Milano	Italy
University Vita-Salute San Raffaele	Italy
National Research Foundation of Korea	Korea
Investment and Development Agency if Latvia	Latvia
Innovation Agency Lithuania	Lithuania
Lithuanian Society for Young Researchers	Lithuania
National Centre for Research and Development	Poland
Citizen Science Lab	Netherlands
Innovation Norway	Norway
Norwegian Association for Local and Regional Authorities	Norway
Norland Research Institute	Norway
Ciencia Viva	Portugal
Innovation Fund Serbia	Serbia
Serbia Centre for the Promotion of Science	Serbia
Fundacion Ibercivis	Spain
Association for Science and Discovery Centres	United Kingdom
UK Foreign Commonwealth and Development	United Kingdom

Office	
UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
Eureka Association	International
European Federation for Older Persons (EURAG)	International
European Network of Living Labs	International
REWAISE Project EU	International
SISCODE Project EU	International
Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development	International

Annex 2: Workshop agendas

Agenda for workshop 1, delivered January 28, 2023

(GMT) 13:00 - 13:05	Welcome & introduction to PRO-Ethics <i>Alex Glennie, Senior Policy Manager (Nesta)</i>
13:05 - 13:30	Getting to know the room - participant introductions
13:30 - 13:40	Presentation: Findings from year one <i>Kalli Giannelos, Researcher on Innovation Ethics (Sciences Po)</i>
13:40 - 14:15	Discussion: Do the needs identified in PRO-Ethics match with those experienced by your organisation?
Break	
14:20 - 14:30	Presentation: The ethics framework <i>Kalli Giannelos, Researcher on Innovation Ethics (Sciences Po)</i>
14:30 - 15:15	Breakout activity: What is the potential for the application of an ethics framework?
15:15 - 15:30	Closing & Q&A: Next steps <i>Dorothea Sturn, Scientific Project Manager (ZSI)</i>

Agenda for workshop 2, delivered April 28, 2021

(CET) 10:00 - 10:20	Welcome & introduction to PRO-Ethics <i>Alex Glennie, Senior Policy Manager (Nesta)</i>
10:20 - 10:40	Getting to know the room - participant introductions
10:40 - 10:50	Presentation: PRO-Ethics' case studies
10:50 - 11:30	Activity: Breakout group discussions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>When is it necessary to involve citizens in your work and when is it not?</i> 2. <i>What practical conditions need to be in place for effective participation?</i>
11:30 - 11:40	Group reconvene: Summary of discussions
Break	
11:50 - 12:00	Intervention: How has citizen science built trust with communities? <i>Margaret Gold, Citizen Science Lab</i>
12:00 - 12:25	Q&A and discussion
12:25 - 12:30	Closing

Agenda for workshop 3, delivered March 22, 2023

(CET) 11:00 - 11:10	Welcome <i>Alex Glennie, Senior Policy Manager (Nesta)</i>
11:10 - 11:20	Introduction: Making the case for citizen participation in R&I <i>Stefanie Schuerz, Project Lead (ZSI)</i>
11:20 - 11:35	Presentation: PRO-Ethics' framework <i>Martijn Wiarda, Researcher (TUD)</i>
11:35 - 11:50	Q&A
Break	
11:55 - 12:35	Breakout group discussions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What responsibilities do you have in the research process to ensure ethical conduct? 2. Feedback on PRO-Ethics; how could this guideline help your organisation and what could be improved?
12:35 - 13:00	Final discussion & closing

Annex 3: Workshop materials

Materials for workshop 1, delivered January 28, 2023

Activity 1.			
		Participant 1	Participant 2
	<p>Please provide any individual feedback, comments or open questions you have related to the ethical framework in the space below.</p> <p>You <i>may</i> want to reflect on:</p> <p>Q1: How practical would a framework like this be?</p> <p>Q2: What support would you need to help adapt this framework so that it useful to your organisation?</p>		
		Participant 3	Participant 4

Figure 3: Activity 1 - Providing feedback on potential application of PRO-Ethics' framework and practical support or adaptation that may be required.

Materials for workshop 2, delivered April 28, 2021

Figure 4: Activity 1 - 'When is it necessary to involve citizens in your work and when is it not?'

Figure 5: Activity 2 - 'What practical conditions need to be in place for effective citizen participation in research and innovation'

Materials for workshop 3, delivered March 22, 2023

Discussion 1

What responsibilities do you have in the research process to ensure ethical conduct?

Discussion 2

How might PROEthics' guidelines help your organisation?

Figure 6: Discussion 1 and 2 - Gathering the ethical responsibilities of research funders and feedback on PRO-Ethics' guidelines ability to support specific contexts.